

METACOGNITIVE AWARENESS OF GRADE 8 STUDENTS AT ROXAS NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL: ITS RELATION TO STUDENTS' MATHEMATICAL PROBLEM-SOLVING SKILLS

Maricar G. Ritan
Mai Rani Khristine A. Zipagan

Saint Ferdinand College-City of Ilagan Campus, City of Ilagan, Isabela, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the meta-cognitive awareness of Grade 8 students at Roxas National High School and its relationship to their ability to solve similar types of mathematical problems in intermediate algebra. Meta-cognitive awareness plays a crucial role in problem-solving, particularly in mathematics, where students' ability to plan, monitor, and evaluate their thinking process is essential for success. Despite the importance of this skill, students often struggle with applying mathematical concepts to real-life situations. This study aims to assess the meta-cognitive awareness of students in solving algebraic problems, focusing on both their knowledge of cognition and regulation of cognition. By using tools like the Metacognitive Awareness Inventory (MAI) and analyzing students' performance in algebra, the research explores the connection between students' awareness of their cognitive processes and their mathematical problem-solving abilities. The results show a significant relationship between students' meta-cognitive strategies and their proficiency in algebra, with planning and conditional knowledge being key factors in effective problem-solving. The study concludes by providing recommendations for teachers, students, and school leaders to enhance metacognitive skills, ultimately improving students' performance in mathematics.

Keywords: *Meta-cognitive awareness, Problem-solving, Intermediate algebra, Mathematical performance, Metacognitive strategies*

INTRODUCTION

Mathematics is a major part of education and builds the basic skills students need for logical thinking, analyzing information, and problem-solving. However, being good at math involves more than just knowing formulas and solving equations; it also requires students to be aware of their own thinking process.

Mathematical problem solving, particularly in Algebra, is a fundamental skill that underpins success in advanced mathematics and STEM disciplines. Problem solving is a vital aspect of Mathematics since it enhances a student's meta-cognitive skill. Despite its importance, students often struggle with effectively applying mathematical concepts to real-life problems. This struggle can be attributed to various factors, with low meta-cognitive awareness being a significant one.

This study aims to investigate the meta-cognitive awareness of Grade 8 students of Roxas National High School and its relationship to their ability to solve similar types of mathematical problems in intermediate algebra.

Recent evaluations have pointed out a decline in students' performance in mathematics on standardized tests. According to national and international assessments, such as the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA), students struggle significantly with problem-solving tasks that require higher-order thinking skills (OECD, 2019). This decline stresses the need to investigate underlying factors, such as metacognitive awareness, that contribute to these performance issues. Based on the 2018 PISA Assessment, the Philippines' average score in mathematics performance ranks among the lowest compared to other participating countries and economies, placing 73rd out of 75.

The PISA 2022 latest results continued to highlight the struggles of Filipino students, particularly in mathematics, where the country ranked sixth from the bottom, showing little improvement from the 2018 PISA results, which reported a similar performance. Despite improvements in students' curiosity and engagement, these factors have not translated into significant advancements in mathematical problem-solving skills. Filipino students continue to face challenges in applying mathematical knowledge to real-life situations. These persistent difficulties emphasize the importance of enhancing meta-cognitive skills and problem-solving strategies in mathematics to improve student outcomes. The Philippines' continued low performance in PISA underscores the need for more effective teaching methods and educational reforms to address these issues. As a result, there is an urgent need to focus on student performance in mathematics in the Philippines. (OECD, 2023)

The implementation of the K-12 curriculum in the Philippines marks a pivotal reform in its educational system, placing emphasis on fostering critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Nevertheless, despite these advancements, a considerable number of students continue to face difficulties in applying mathematical concepts to address challenges. This underscores the necessity for targeted interventions, including the enhancement of meta-cognitive skills, as suggested by the Department of Education.

Research, according to Zepeda et. al (2015) has shown that meta-cognitive skills are crucial for successful learning and problem solving. Students who are meta-cognitively aware are better at planning, monitoring, and evaluating their cognitive processes, which leads to improved academic performance. By focusing on meta-cognitive awareness, educators can help students develop these essential skills, thereby enhancing their problem-solving abilities in algebra.

Developing metacognitive awareness is important for helping students solve math problems effectively. However, many students have trouble understanding and controlling their thinking, making it hard for them to use problem-solving strategies in new situations.

In Grade 8 math, the researcher has noticed that while some students are good at following steps, they often struggle with planning, checking, and adjusting their work. Through informal classroom conversations and activities, it became clear that students with better metacognitive awareness do better at solving problems because they can change their approach when needed.

These observations show how important it is to help students improve their metacognitive skills. This study aims to look at how metacognitive awareness affects students' problem-solving skills and provide ideas for improving math teaching.

There is limited research specifically addressing the meta-cognitive awareness of students in the Philippines, particularly within the context of Roxas National High School. Conducting this study will offer valuable perspectives into the distinct requirements and obstacles encountered by these students. This, in turn, will facilitate the creation of customized interventions aimed at augmenting their proficiency in mathematical problem-solving.

In Roxas National High School in Isabela, Philippines, teachers noticed a discrepancy in Grade 8 students' ability to effectively solve problems in intermediate of similar types despite receiving instruction on the same concepts. While some students demonstrate a strong grasp of intermediate algebra principles and applied appropriate problem-solving strategies, others exhibit difficulties in understanding the underlying processes and approaches. This observation raised questions about the students' meta-cognitive awareness—their understanding and regulation of their own cognitive processes—in relation to problem solving in intermediate algebra. Given the importance of mathematics education in the Philippine curriculum and the need to ensure equitable learning outcomes for all students, there was a recognized necessity to investigate the meta-cognitive awareness of Grade 8 students and its relation for their solution strategies in solving problems in intermediate algebra.

Based from the evaluation of students in grade 7 last school year 2022- 2023, including students in special and regular curriculum indicate 1.56% in mastered level, 2.60% in closely approximating mastery level, 9.90% in progressing towards mastery level, average mastery level is 48%, 36.9% had low mastery, 1.04% had very low mastery, and 0.00% had absolutely no mastery in 12 learning competencies.

This implies that while a small percentage of students have achieved a high level of mastery, the majority of students fall within the average or lower mastery levels. Specifically, 36.9% of students demonstrated low mastery, and 1.04% had very low mastery, highlighting a significant portion of students who may require additional support to reach proficiency in these competencies. The 48% of students at the average mastery level suggests that many students have a basic understanding but are not fully proficient, indicating room for improvement in teaching methods or learning strategies. Furthermore, the absence of students at the absolutely no mastery level indicates that all students have some foundational understanding, which is a positive sign but still points to the need for targeted interventions and differentiated instruction to elevate the performance of students in lower mastery levels. This distribution underscores the importance of addressing the varying needs of students, potentially through strategies like metacognitive awareness, to enhance their problem-solving skills and help them progress towards higher levels of mastery.

Given this context, Roxas National High School provides an ideal setting for collecting data on the mathematical meta-cognitive awareness of Grade 8 students in algebra for the 2024–2025 school year. With these, this study aims to determine the student's meta-cognitive awareness and its relation on students' mathematical problem-solving skills.

Research Questions

This study aimed to assess the meta-cognitive awareness of Grade 8 students in solving similar types of intermediate algebra problems.

Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What are the students' key profile in terms of:
 2. Sex; and
 3. grade in Math
2. What is the level of student's metacognitive awareness in solving similar types of intermediate algebra problems in terms of:
 1. Knowledge of cognition
 - Declarative Knowledge
 - Procedural Knowledge
 - Conditional Knowledge
 2. Regulation of Cognition
 - Planning
 - Comprehension Monitoring
 - Information Management Strategies
 - Debugging Strategies
 - Evaluation
3. Is there a significant difference in the meta-cognitive strategies used by the students in problem-solving when grouped according to their profile?
4. What is the proficiency level of the students in problem solving in Intermediate Algebra?

5. How do the meta-cognitive strategies utilized by students significantly relate to their problem-solving skills in intermediate algebra?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative research design to examine Grade 8 students' metacognitive awareness related to their problem-solving processes in intermediate algebra. The research focuses on measuring students' metacognitive awareness using standardized tools such as the Metacognitive Awareness Inventory (MAI) and assessing their performance on algebra problem-solving tasks. The data were analyzed with statistical methods to identify patterns and trends based on variables like gender and math grade. Specifically, the study used descriptive statistics to summarize students' profiles and problem-solving performance, while the weighted mean assessed their level of metacognitive awareness. One-Way ANOVA determined significant differences in the metacognitive strategies used by students during problem-solving when grouped by their profiles. Additionally, Pearson's r-Test examined the correlation between students' metacognitive strategies and their problem-solving skills in intermediate algebra. By focusing on measurable data, this study aimed to provide a clear understanding of how metacognitive awareness influences students' problem-solving abilities in algebra, relying on robust statistical analysis to answer the research questions.

Locale of the Study

This research was conducted at Roxas National High School in Roxas, Isabela. The school follows the K-12 Basic Education Curriculum and offers specialized programs for advanced students, including the Science, Technology, and Engineering (STE) program, the Special Program in the Arts (SPA), and the Special Program in Journalism (SPJ). To help teachers improve their teaching methods, the school provides In-Service Training (INSET). Roxas National High School also actively encourages student participation in mathematics competitions, such as the Mathematics Teachers Association of the Philippines (MTAP), where the school's representative placed within the top five in 2019. Additionally, in the PATH-MATH Contest held on December 14, 2022, at Tumauni National High School, the school's representative progressed to the division level, earning fifth place among schools in the Province of Isabela.

Selection and Description of Respondents

The respondents of this research are Grade 8 students at Roxas National High School for the 2024-2025 school year. The researcher used stratified random sampling to select the sample, ensuring proportional representation from each of the 12 sections. This includes a diverse group of Grade 8 students, typically aged around 13-14 years old, consisting of both male and female students and representing various academic proficiency levels: Beginning, Developing, Approaching Proficiency, Proficient, and Advanced learners.

To ensure an equitable distribution of respondents from each section, the researcher applied stratified random sampling, considering the enrollment size of each section. The number of students selected from each section is proportional to its total enrollment, thereby maintaining an accurate representation of the entire Grade 8 population at Roxas National High School. This method also account for students' proficiency levels, determined by their mathematics average grades.

To determine the sample size, Slovin's formula was applied to the total population of Grade 8 students, which is 490. The margin of error (e) is set at 5%, resulting in a required sample size of approximately 220 students. This sample size ensures that the study's results is statistically valid and representative of the Grade 8 population at Roxas National High School within the specified margin of error.

Using this approach, the sample is a representative of all proficiency levels—Beginning, Developing, Approaching Proficiency, Proficient, and Advanced—ensuring that every proficiency level is adequately represented in the final sample for the study.

Table 1
Sample of the Research

Section	Population	Sample Size
Einstein	40	18
Euclid	37	17
Gemini	43	19
Leo	43	19
Libra	39	18
Pisces	44	20
Sagittarius	43	19
Scorpio	42	19
SPA-A	45	20
SPA-B	42	19
SPJ	30	13
Virgo	42	19
TOTAL	490	220

Data Gathering Procedure

Initially, this research started with a demographic survey that was administered to all participating students to collect key profile information such as sex, and proficiency level. This survey was designed to gather data anonymously and confidentially through paper-based surveys. Concurrently, standardized assessments measuring metacognitive awareness, such as the Metacognitive Awareness Inventory (MAI) developed by Schraw and Dennison, and the construction of problems in intermediate algebra guided by the

Department of Education's Most Essential Learning Competencies, will be administered to 220 Grade 8 students to assess their metacognitive abilities.

The sample of 220 students were selected using stratified random sampling, ensuring proportional representation from the 12 Grade 8 sections at Roxas National High School. The strata were based on gender and proficiency level, with students grouped according to these characteristics. Proficiency levels was determined by their mathematics average grades. Within each stratum, students were randomly selected, ensuring an equitable distribution of gender and proficiency across the sample.

The average grades of the students from the first to third quarter were used to determine their proficiency levels in mathematics. These grades were collected from the class records with the assistance of their respective teachers to ensure accuracy and consistency in data collection.

The selected students then completed the MAI survey and the mathematical problem set in algebra. Once all data is collected, the researcher encoded and analyzed it to draw conclusions and provide recommendations.

Statistical Treatment of Data

To analyze the gathered data, the following statistical treatment were used:

Frequency and Percentage Count. This was used to determine the student's key profile including sex and math grade and the proficiency level of the students in problem solving in intermediate algebra problems.

Weighted Mean. This was utilized to assess the metacognitive awareness of the students used in solving similar types of intermediate algebra problems.

ANOVA. It was employed to test the significant difference in the metacognitive strategies used by the students in problem solving when grouped according to their profiles.

Pearson's r-Test. This was applied to determine the impact of the metacognitive strategies utilized by the students to their problem-solving skills in intermediate algebra.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. What are the students' key profile in terms of:

a. **Sex**

Table 2
Student's Profile in Terms of Sex

Sex	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Male	118	53.6

Female	102	46.4
Total	220	100

Table 2 presents the distribution of respondents according to their sex. Analyzing the gender composition allows for a better understanding of whether metacognitive awareness and problem-solving strategies differ between male and female students.

As shown in the table, 118 students or 53.6% are male, while 102 students or 46.4% are female. This distribution shows a slightly higher number of male respondents than female respondents. The relatively balanced representation of both sexes enables a more meaningful comparison in analyzing potential gender differences in metacognitive awareness and problem-solving strategies, which will be further examined in the succeeding sections.

The nearly equal distribution of male and female students in this study helps ensure that the results are unbiased and not influenced by gender. This balance allows the researcher to examine any potential differences between male and female students in terms of how they use metacognitive strategies and approach problem-solving.

b. Grade in Math

**Table 3
Student's Profile in Terms of Mathematics Grade**

Mathematics Grade	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
90-100 (Advanced)	45	20.5
85-89 (Proficient)	73	33.2
80-84 (Approaching Proficiency)	38	17.3
75-79 (Developing)	31	14.1
74 and below (Beginning)	33	15.0
Total	220	100

Table 3 presents the distribution of respondents based on their Mathematics average grade from the 1st to 3rd Quarter. Analyzing students' academic performance helps in understanding whether metacognitive awareness influences their problem-solving proficiency in Intermediate Algebra.

As shown in the table, the largest proportion of students, or 33.2% are classified as Proficient (85-89), indicating that they have strong mathematical skills and problem-solving abilities. Additionally, 20.5% are in the Advanced (90-100) category, showcasing exceptional performance in Mathematics. Meanwhile, 17.3% are in the Approaching Proficiency (80-84) category, meaning they are close to achieving mastery but still need some improvement.

On the other hand, 14.1% are in the Developing (75-79) category, and 15.0% fall under the Beginning (74 and below) level, indicating that they require additional support to strengthen their mathematical skills.

These results reveal that a significant portion of students demonstrate strong mathematical abilities, with 46.4% of students (Developing, Beginning, and Approaching Proficiency) still need improvement.

3. What is the level of student’s metacognitive awareness in solving similar types of intermediate algebra problems in terms of:

1. Students’ General Metacognitive Awareness

Table 4
Students’ General Metacognitive Awareness Level

Metacognitive Awareness Components	Mean	Interpretation
Knowledge of Cognition		
Declarative	3.73	High
Procedural	3.72	High
Conditional	3.78	High
Regulation of Cognition		
Planning	3.84	High
Comprehension Monitoring	3.73	High
Information Management Strategies	3.71	High
Debugging	3.79	High
Evaluation	3.68	High

Table 4 presents the description of students' general metacognitive awareness in solving intermediate algebra problems. The table includes the mean and the interpretation of each metacognitive awareness component.

As shown in the table, the students in the study generally exhibit *high* level of metacognitive awareness in solving intermediate algebra problems, with mean scores ranging from 3.68 to 3.84 across all components. The Conditional Knowledge component recorded the highest mean score of 3.78, indicating that students show greater awareness of when and why specific strategies should be applied. This suggests their ability to determine under what conditions certain processes or skills transfer, and to apply declarative and procedural knowledge appropriately based on the situation. This result supports Schraw and Dennison’s (1994) finding that well-developed conditional knowledge underpins effective strategy selection.

Procedural Knowledge recorded the lowest mean score of 3.720, yet it still reflects a high level of awareness regarding how to carry out mathematical procedures. This suggests that students know how to implement appropriate strategies, understand the steps involved in completing a process, and recognize when to apply these steps in various contexts. This finding supports Flavell’s (1979) metacognitive framework, which

differentiates procedural knowledge—knowing how—from declarative knowledge—knowing what.

Under the Regulation of Cognition components, Planning recorded the highest mean score of 3.84, indicating that students tend to engage in planning, goal setting, and resource allocation prior to solving problems. This finding aligns with Zimmerman’s (2002) model of self-regulated learning, which emphasizes the importance of forethought in effective academic performance.

Conversely, Evaluation recorded the lowest mean score of 3.677, suggesting that students engage less frequently in analyzing their performance and the effectiveness of their strategies after completing a task. This supports Schoenfeld’s (1992) view that evaluation is a critical component of problem-solving, essential for verifying and refining one’s work.

a. Knowledge of Cognition

Table 5
Student’s Metacognitive Awareness Level on Knowledge of Cognition

Knowledge of Cognition	Mean	Interpretation
Declarative Knowledge Question		
• Q5	3.89	High
• Q10	4.00	High
• Q12	3.55	High
• Q16	3.61	High
• Q17	3.51	High
• Q20	3.54	High
• Q32	3.58	High
• Q46	4.18	High
Procedural Knowledge Question		
• Q3	3.86	High
• Q14	3.65	High
• Q27	3.78	High
• Q33	3.59	High
Conditional Knowledge Question		
• Q15	4.21	Very High
• Q18	3.67	High
• Q26	3.77	High
• Q29	3.64	High
• Q35	3.59	High

Further analysis of students’ responses to individual items under each component of metacognitive awareness provides deeper insight into their specific strengths and areas for development. As shown in Table 5, all items under Declarative, Procedural, and Conditional Knowledge were interpreted as **High**, with one item (Q15) under Conditional Knowledge rated as **Very High**, having a mean score of 4.21. This suggests that the majority of students are particularly confident in determining appropriate strategies and knowing when and why to apply them—an essential aspect of strategic problem-solving

and a key indicator of well-developed conditional knowledge. The highest-rated item in Declarative Knowledge, Q46, with a mean score of 4.18, suggests that students possess a strong awareness of their own skills, intellectual resources, and learning preferences. This involves knowing what, or that, and understanding one's abilities as a learner. The finding highlights its importance in academic performance. Such awareness enables students to apply their knowledge effectively by recognizing their own strengths and utilizing appropriate strategies in various learning contexts.

In contrast, slightly lower yet still high on items such as Q17 with mean score of 3.51 and Q20 with mean score of 3.54 under Declarative Knowledge suggest that while students are aware of the strategies they employ, they may not always have a clear understanding of when or why these strategies are most effective.

Similarly, the high but slightly lower scores on some Procedural Knowledge items suggest that while students are aware of how to implement learning procedures for solving algebraic problems, they may still require more practice to effectively apply these procedures in various situations and to do so with greater consistency and efficiency.

2. Regulation of Cognition

Table 6
Student's Metacognitive Awareness Level on Regulation of Cognition

Regulation of Cognition	Mean	Interpretation
Planning Question		
• Q4	3.71	High
• Q6	4.00	High
• Q8	3.68	High
• Q22	3.75	High
• Q23	3.82	High
• Q42	4.04	High
• Q45	3.85	High
Comprehension Monitoring Question		
• Q1	3.82	High
• Q2	3.70	High
• Q11	3.76	High
• Q21	3.66	High
• Q28	3.79	High
• Q34	3.74	High
• Q49	3.66	High
Information Management		
• Q9	3.95	High
• Q13	3.78	High
• Q30	3.88	High
• Q31	3.50	High
• Q37	3.43	High
• Q39	3.75	High
• Q41	3.72	High

• Q43	3.87	High
• Q47	3.61	High
• Q48	3.60	High
Debugging		
• Q25	3.91	High
• Q40	3.78	High
• Q44	3.69	High
• Q51	3.62	High
• Q52	3.95	High
Evaluation Question		
• Q7	3.75	High
• Q19	3.89	High
• Q24	3.60	High
• Q36	3.67	High
• Q38	3.65	High
• Q50	3.51	High

As detailed in Table 6, all components under Regulation of Cognition also received **High** interpretations, reflecting a generally strong capacity among students to manage and regulate their learning processes. Items under Planning, such as Q42 with mean score of 4.04 and Q6 with mean score of 4.00 yielded some of the highest means in this component, reinforcing earlier findings in Table 4-A that planning is a key metacognitive strength for students.

However, certain items under Information Management Strategies and Evaluation, such as Q37 with mean score of 3.43, Q50, mean score of 3.51, and Q36, mean score of 3.67, though still interpreted as High, reflect relatively lower awareness. This suggests that students may need more structured guidance in organizing and checking their work thoroughly.

These item-level insights affirm that while students generally show a strong metacognitive foundation, targeted interventions that reinforce procedural fluency, evaluative thinking, and reflective checking could further enhance their mathematical problem-solving capabilities. Teachers may consider integrating activities that require students to verbalize their procedures, reflect on errors, and evaluate alternate solution paths to strengthen these areas.

These findings show that students are slightly stronger in regulating their cognition especially in terms of planning than in their knowledge of cognition, particularly procedural knowledge. This echoes Polya's (2004) emphasis on the need for explicit instructional support in procedural practice and reflective evaluation to bolster mathematical problem-solving proficiency.

The results suggest that students demonstrate a good level of metacognitive awareness, particularly in planning and conditional knowledge, which are essential for selecting appropriate strategies and preparing for problem-solving tasks. However, the relatively lower awareness of procedural knowledge and evaluation indicates that there are areas where students could improve, specifically in applying mathematical

procedures and reviewing their work. This implies that teachers may need to focus more on developing students' procedural knowledge through targeted practice and reinforcing the importance of evaluation as part of the problem-solving process. Providing more structured opportunities for students to engage in reflective practices, such as checking and revising their solutions, could significantly enhance their overall problem-solving proficiency.

4. Is there a significant difference in the meta-cognitive strategies used by the students in problem-solving when grouped according to their profile?

Table 7
Result of the test of Significant Difference in the Meta-cognitive Strategies Used by the Students in Problem-solving when grouped according to their Profile

Profile	Significance (F)	Decision	Remarks
Sex	.004	Reject Ho	There is a Significant Difference
Math Average Grade (1st to 3rd)	.014	Reject Ho	There is a Significant Difference

Table 7 shows the result of the test significant differences in the metacognitive strategies used by the students in problem-solving when grouped according to their profile using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) F-test at a 0.05 level of significance.

As shown, the significance F-values for the profile sex and Math Average Grade for the 1st to 3rd quarter of the respondents are less than .05 which resulted to the rejection of null hypothesis Ho. This statistically indicates that there is a significant difference in the meta-cognitive strategies used by the students in problem-solving when grouped according to their profile sex and Math Average Grade (1st to 3rd).

Result indicates that meta-cognitive strategies used by the students in problem-solving is significantly related to their sex and Math Average Grade. The findings imply that female students, particularly those with average grades on Math greater than or equal to 90 tend to exhibit higher levels of metacognitive awareness.

These findings align with previous studies that highlight the role of metacognitive awareness in enhancing academic performance and problem-solving skills. Baguin and Janiola (2004) , Schraw and Dennison (1994), Özsoy (2011), Desoete (2019), and Schoenfeld (1992) which emphasize that high metacognitive awareness is often linked to better academic outcomes. The current results reinforce this idea, particularly in the context of students with higher Math grades, whose metacognitive strategies appear to be more developed and effective in problem-solving.

5. What is the proficiency level of the students in problem solving in Intermediate Algebra?

Table 8
Students' Proficiency Levels in Problem Solving in Intermediate Algebra

Proficiency Level	Percentage Score	Frequency	Percentage
Advanced	90-100	1	0.5%
Proficient	85-89	2	0.9%
Approaching Proficiency	80-84	4	1.8%
Developing	75-79	1	0.5%
Beginning	74 and below	212	96.4%

Table 8 presents the frequency distribution of students' proficiency levels in solving 5-item intermediate algebra problems. The results show that the majority or 96.4% of students are have a Beginning Proficiency level, indicating that most students of Roxas National High School face difficulties in solving intermediate algebra problems. A smaller percentage of students are Proficient with 0.9% and Approaching Proficiency with 1.8%, while 0.5% of students have Advanced proficiency level.

Research shows that students often face challenges in solving complex mathematical problems, especially as they move beyond basic procedural knowledge. According to Polya (2004), effective problem-solving requires not only understanding basic concepts but also applying them in novel situations. However, many students struggle to transition from understanding isolated facts to applying those facts in problem-solving tasks. This aligns with the results of this study, where a significant number of students were classified as beginning in proficiency with 96.4%, indicating that they may have difficulties in applying intermediate algebra concepts to real-world problems.

Metacognitive awareness plays an essential role in developing effective problem-solving strategies. Schraw and Moshman (1995) argue that students with high levels of metacognitive awareness can better monitor and control their thought processes, enabling them to approach problems more effectively. However, as this study's findings suggest, many students of Roxas National High School may lack the necessary metacognitive strategies to solve more complex mathematical problems, which contributes to their lower proficiency levels. Schraw and Dennison (1994) emphasized the importance of metacognitive knowledge and regulation in enhancing academic performance, suggesting that the lack of these skills may explain why students in this study exhibited lower proficiency in problem-solving.

Baguin and Janiola (2024) also observed that students with greater metacognitive awareness tend to have higher achievement in mathematics. This finding is consistent with this study, where the majority of students at the Beginning proficiency level likely face challenges in managing and monitoring their cognitive processes during problem-solving, which could be addressed by improving their metacognitive strategies.

6. How do the meta-cognitive strategies utilized by students significantly relate to their problem-solving skills in intermediate algebra?

Table 9
Result of the Test of Significant Relationship Between the Meta-cognitive Strategies Utilized by Students and Their Problem-solving Skills in Intermediate Algebra

Group	Significance <i>r</i>	Decision	Remarks
Meta-cognitive Awareness along Knowledge of Cognition and Problem-solving Skills in Intermediate Algebra	<0.000	Reject Ho	There is a significant relationship
Meta-cognitive Awareness along Regulation of Cognition and Problem-solving Skills in Intermediate Algebra	<0.000	Reject Ho	There is a significant relationship
Overall Average Metacognitive Awareness and Problem-solving Skills in Intermediate Algebra	<0.000	Reject Ho	There is a significant relationship

Table 9 reveals the result of the test of significant relationship between the meta-cognitive strategies utilized by students and their problem-solving skills in intermediate algebra using Pearson's Coefficient of Correlation *r*-test at .05 level of significance.

As can be seen, the significance *r*-values for the groups Meta-cognitive Awareness along Knowledge of Cognition and Problem-solving Skills in Intermediate Algebra; Meta-cognitive Awareness along Regulation of Cognition and Problem-solving Skills in Intermediate Algebra; and, the Overall Average Meta-Cognitive Awareness and Problem-solving Skills in Intermediate Algebra are less than .05, which resulted in the rejection of the null hypothesis. This statistically indicates that there is a significant relationship between the meta-cognitive strategies utilized by students, along Knowledge of Cognition, along with Regulation of Cognition, and Overall Average Meta-Awareness, and, their problem-solving skills in intermediate algebra.

The respondents' problem-solving Skills in Intermediate Algebra are significantly correlated to the meta-cognitive strategies utilized by them along Knowledge of Cognition, Regulation of Cognition and, the Overall Average Meta-Cognitive Awareness.

Hence, respondents' problem-solving skills in Intermediate Algebra are significantly affected by their Meta-cognitive Awareness along Knowledge of Cognition, along Regulation of Cognition, and, the Overall Average Meta-Cognitive Awareness.

Metacognitive awareness plays a pivotal role in enhancing students' problem-solving abilities, particularly in the field of mathematics. Research by Brown (1987), Flavell (1979), and Schraw & Moshman (1995) emphasize the significance of both metacognitive knowledge and regulation in fostering effective learning. Students who possess an awareness of their cognitive processes—such as planning, evaluating, and reflecting on their problem-solving strategies—are better equipped to approach and solve mathematical problems. This aligns with the concept of self-regulated learning, as described by Zimmerman (2002), wherein students set goals, monitor their progress, and adjust their strategies to optimize academic performance.

In the context of mathematics, where selecting appropriate problem-solving strategies is essential, metacognitive awareness enables students to identify and correct errors, as highlighted by Polya (2004). This reflective process not only enhances the efficiency of their approach but also deepens their understanding of mathematical concepts. Research by Schraw and Dennison (1994) and Özsoy (2011) demonstrates a positive correlation between metacognitive skills and higher academic performance in mathematics, underscoring the importance of integrating these strategies into instructional practices.

Nevertheless, certain studies, such as those by Artelt and Schneider (2015), suggest that students who face challenges in mathematics may not fully benefit from metacognitive strategies without supplementary support. This underscores the need for differentiated instruction, particularly for students with lower levels of metacognitive awareness, ensuring that they receive adequate guidance to develop these essential skills.

Metacognitive awareness is anticipated to be a key determinant in students' proficiency in solving intermediate algebra problems. The findings from existing research strongly support the notion that fostering metacognitive skills will enhance students' problem-solving effectiveness and, in turn, improve their overall mathematical performance.

Furthermore, the results of the students' performance across Polya's (2004) four steps of problem-solving reveal where they encounter the most difficulty. Based on the computed mean scores, students scored 0.95 out of 1 in Understanding the Problem, 0.53 out of 1 in Devising a Plan, 1.16 out of 2 in Carrying Out the Plan, and only 0.202 out of 1 in Checking the Result. These results indicate that students found devising a plan and especially checking the result, the most challenging steps to execute. The notably low score in the checking step indicates that students struggle to evaluate and reflect on

their solutions, which is a crucial aspect of metacognitive regulation. This supports the significant role of metacognitive strategies in problem-solving, particularly in planning and evaluating solutions—core aspects of metacognitive regulation.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions are drawn:

The study showed that students' metacognitive awareness, including both Knowledge of Cognition and Regulation of Cognition, has a strong link to their problem-solving skills in intermediate algebra. This suggests that students who are more aware of how they think, which strategies to use, when to apply them, and how to regulate their thinking process are more likely to perform better at solving algebraic problems.

The results highlight the importance of developing both parts of metacognitive awareness. On one side, Knowledge of Cognition such as declarative, procedural, and conditional knowledge helps students understand mathematical content and strategies. On the other side, Regulation of Cognition including planning, comprehension monitoring, information management, debugging, and evaluation gives students the skills to manage their thinking, adjust their approaches, and reflect effectively during problem-solving.

Thus, improving students' metacognitive strategies holistically, not just in regulation but also in knowledge, can significantly enhance their mathematical performance in intermediate algebra.

Recommendations

The findings of this study highlight the importance of metacognitive awareness in improving students' problem-solving skills in Intermediate Algebra. To address the areas where students need support, the following recommendations are provided. These aim to enhance metacognitive skills and problem-solving abilities, benefiting both teachers and students in the learning process.

For teachers:

- Integrate activities like think-alouds, self-questioning, reflection journals, and collaborative problem-solving into math lessons to enhance students' metacognitive awareness.
- Design math problems that connect algebra to practical applications to help students recognize the relevance of mathematical concepts.
- Assess students' metacognitive awareness regularly alongside their academic performance to identify areas where students need additional support, and provide targeted interventions.
- Provide extra help for students struggling with problem-solving, such as peer tutoring and step-by-step guidance on basic algebra concepts.

- Offer additional support to male students with lower metacognitive awareness through group problem-solving activities and explicit instruction on self-monitoring strategies.
- Provide worked examples, and encourage reflection on mistakes to improve both math skills and metacognitive awareness for students with grades of 74 and below.
- Participate in professional development programs focused on teaching metacognitive strategies and assessing and nurturing students' metacognitive growth.
- Encourage parents to help students develop metacognitive skills at home by asking them to explain their problem-solving processes.

For School Leaders:

- Offer professional development on metacognitive teaching methods, including workshops or resources to help teachers integrate these strategies.
- Create opportunities for teachers to collaborate and share strategies for improving metacognitive awareness in the classroom.
- Establish regular communication between teachers and parents, focusing on supporting students' metacognitive development.

For Learners:

- Engage in activities like thinking aloud while solving problems, asking themselves self-reflective questions, and keeping a math journal to enhance their awareness of the problem-solving process.
- Apply algebra concepts to everyday life scenarios, such as managing a budget or planning a project, to see the practical value of their learning.
- Take time to reflect on their problem-solving approaches after completing tasks, noting areas for improvement and how they can adjust their strategies in the future.
- Seek support from peers, teachers, or online resources to reinforce their understanding and improve both their mathematical skills and metacognitive awareness for those who find certain algebraic concepts challenging.
- Reflect on errors is an important step in strengthening both problem-solving skills and metacognitive awareness. Students should actively review mistakes and consider alternative strategies for better solutions.

For Future Researchers:

- Investigate how metacognitive awareness impacts problem-solving across various math areas.
- Study how metacognitive skills vary by gender to create tailored interventions.
- Focus on strategies to boost metacognitive awareness and problem-solving in students with lower grades.
- Research how metacognitive skills help students solve real-life problems, linking classroom learning to practical use.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adheres to the highest ethical standards to ensure the integrity and confidentiality of all participants involved. Informed consent was obtained from all participants and their parents or guardians prior to participation. Participants were provided with clear information about the purpose of the study, the methods used, and their right to withdraw from the study at any time without penalty. Confidentiality and anonymity were maintained throughout the research process, with participants being assigned identification codes instead of using personal identifiers. All data collected was securely stored and only accessible to authorized personnel. Participation in the study was voluntary, and students were informed that they could choose to withdraw at any point without affecting their academic standing. The research was designed to minimize any physical, emotional, or psychological harm, ensuring that activities such as surveys and problem-solving tasks did not cause undue stress. Transparency and honesty were prioritized, with the objectives of the study clearly communicated and the findings reported truthfully. The research design, methodology, and instruments were reviewed and approved by the institutional review board (IRB) to ensure compliance with ethical guidelines. Throughout the study, the researcher respected the autonomy of participants, providing them the freedom to share their thoughts and experiences openly. By adhering to these ethical standards, the study aimed to protect participants' rights while maintaining the integrity of the research process.

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REFERENCES

- Artelt, C., & Schneider, W. (2015). Cross-country generalizability of the role of metacognitive knowledge in students' strategy use and reading competence. *Teachers College Record*, 117(1), 1-32. <https://doi.org/10.1177/016146811511700103>
- Baguin, R., & Janiola, F. (2024). Students' level of metacognitive awareness as correlates of their mathematics achievement. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 16(6), 639-646. <https://doi.org/10.6129/pe.v16i6.636>
- Brown, A. L. (1987). Metacognition, executive control, self-regulation, and other more mysterious mechanisms. In F. E. Weinert & R. H. Kluwe (Eds.), *Metacognition, motivation, and understanding* (pp. 65-116). Erlbaum.
- Desoete, A., & De Craene, B. (2019). Metacognition and mathematics education: An overview. *ZDM Mathematics Education*, 51(4), 565-575. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11858-019-01076-4>
- Flavell, J. H. (1979). Metacognition and cognitive monitoring: A new area of cognitive-developmental inquiry. *American Psychologist*, 34(10), 906-911. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.34.10.906>
- OECD. (2019). *PISA 2018 results (Volume I): What students know and can do*. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/5f07c754-en>
- OECD. (2023). *PISA 2022 results (Volume I)*. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/5f07c754-en>
- Özsoy, G. (2011). An investigation of the relationship between metacognition and mathematics achievement. *Asia Pacific Education Review*, 12(2), 227-235. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12564-010-9127-1>
- Polya, G. (2004). *How to solve it: A new aspect of mathematical method* (2nd ed.). Princeton University Press.
- Schoenfeld, A. H. (1992). Learning to think mathematically: Problem solving, metacognition, and sense making in mathematics. *Journal for Research in Mathematics Education*, 23(5), 334-346. <https://doi.org/10.5951/jresmetheduc.23.5.0334>
- Schraw, G., & Dennison, R. (1994). Assessing metacognitive awareness. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 19(4), 460-475. <https://doi.org/10.1006/ceps.1994.1033>
- Schraw, G., & Moshman, D. (1995). Metacognitive theories. *Educational Psychology Review*, 7(4), 351-371. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02212416>
- Zepeda, C. D., Richey, J. E., Ronevich, P., & Nokes-Malach, T. J. (2015). Direct instruction of metacognition benefits adolescent science learning, transfer, and motivation: An in vivo study. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 107(4), 954-970. <https://doi.org/10.1037/edu0000007>

Zimmerman, B. J. (2002). Becoming a self-regulated learner: An overview. *Theory into Practice*, 41(2), 64-70. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15430421tip4102_2